

Bilayer thick structures based on $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{TiO}_2$ composite and niobium-doped PZT obtained by electrophoretic deposition

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Abstract

In view of developing new structures and processes for the production of magnetoelectric materials, bilayer thick structures made of cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4)/titanium dioxide (TiO_2) composite and niobium-doped lead zirconate titanate (PZTN) were grown on silver-coated alumina substrates by electrophoretic deposition (EPD) from ethanol-based colloidal suspensions. A first co-deposition from a $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{TiO}_2$ suspension was followed, after heat treatments of the electrodeposited composite layer, by a second deposition from a PZTN suspension. Each deposition was performed at constant voltage while recording the current. High density structures keeping the same stoichiometry of the deposited particles were observed after sintering. Composition, thickness and relative density of the layers were investigated by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analyses, while the crystalline phases were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Ferroelectric, hysteresis loops and piezoelectric response of the bilayer thick structures were measured resulting in good piezoelectric activity of the poled structures.

Keywords

EPD, PZT, thick bilayer, cobalt ferrite, titanium dioxide.

1. Introduction

The ability to manipulate microstructural features and the easy implementation in processing advanced heterostructured nanomaterials and coatings of the electrophoretic deposition (EPD) technique [1] meet the growing interest in the fabrication of

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magnetolectric (ME) materials. Such materials find application in the production of many
electronic devices, including filters, attenuators, oscillators, phase shifters, field probes,
data storage applications, miniaturized antenna, and cloaks. Advantages of the EPD
technique include low cost and the possibility to create homogeneous and dense
nanostructures [2-4], which can be sintered at lower temperatures [5]. In particular, the
electrophoretic deposition of nanoparticles allows the production of high-density magnetic
data storage materials preventing the increase of the size of superparamagnetic domains
[6]. Multilayered structures based on conventional ferromagnetic and ferroelectric
materials have been proposed in the past and prototypal multiferroics have been
developed in several different combinations of ferromagnetic (spinel, hexaferrites) and
ferroelectric (perovskite) phases [7-13].

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Among spinel structures, cobalt ferrite, CoFe_2O_4 , is one of the best magnetostrictive
materials, as well as niobium-doped lead zirconate titanate (PZTN) ranks as one of the
best piezoelectric oxides among the perovskite structures. In particular, cobalt ferrite is
characterized by a large magnetostrictive coefficient [12,14] and a high magnetocrystalline
anisotropy [15], while niobium-doped lead zirconate titanate (PZTN) with 52/48 Zr/Ti molar
ratio (a soft piezoelectric material) is one of the best performing ferroelectric and
piezoelectric ceramics, displaying high dielectric permittivity ($\epsilon_{33} \sim 1550$) and strong
piezoelectric coupling ($k_p \sim 0.67$) [16]. Previous work demonstrated that the production of
new phases from lead zirconate titanate and ferrites does not significantly occur up to
sintering temperatures of 1100°C [13]. Good crystalline compatibility between the two
phases is also ensured by a less than 4% lattice mismatch [17]. However, more detailed
investigations need to be carried out in order to clarify the ferroelectric effect on the
magnetic constituent, as well as the coupling mechanisms [18,19], the best methods for
estimating the effective material parameters, and the validation of theoretical models [20,
21]. The cobalt ferrite/PZT composite system has been investigated in many different
structural configurations, such as thin films [22], laminated composites [23,24], and self-
assembled nanostructures [25].

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In this paper we considered the possibility to produce bilayer thick structures based on
 CoFe_2O_4 and PZTN by EPD. Moreover, in order to tailor the overall dielectric properties for
the bilayer, a dielectric phase was added to the system. With this aim titanium dioxide
(TiO_2), a well-known dielectric material in each of its naturally occurring polymorphic
phases (anatase, brookite and rutile), was selected. The processing consisted in a first

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electrophoretic co-deposition on silver-coated alumina substrates of CoFe_2O_4 and TiO_2 particles dispersed in an ethanol suspension followed by a first thermal consolidation. Then a second EPD on the formed composite layer from an ethanol-based PZTN suspension was performed followed by a final sintering. The resulting structures were characterized and discussed either from the morphologic and functional (dielectric and piezoelectric properties) point of view. The application of EPD to create such bilayer cobalt ferrite/PZTN structures can be regarded as a first step to the production of novel ME materials for many applications [10], potentially with great industrial and technological benefits.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Suspension preparation and characterization

The stock colloidal suspension of cobalt ferrite (CF henceforth) nanoparticles in diethylene glycol (NAMA06, Colorobbia) with solid load content 2.5 wt% was diluted with absolute ethanol (Fluka) to 0.3 wt% in order to ensure film coagulation during the EPD process [26]. Commercial TiO_2 nanopowders (P25, Degussa) was dispersed in absolute ethanol (Fluka) in presence of 0.5 wt% of alkyl phosphate ester (Phospholan PE65, Akzo Nobel) and 1.3 wt% of polyvinyl butyral (B-98, Butvar), introduced as dispersant and binder, respectively, getting a suspension at 11.5 wt% solid content. Such suspension was homogenized by ball-milling with zirconia spheres [27].

The CF/ TiO_2 suspension for EPD was prepared by mixing 50 mL of CF suspension with 0.35 mL of TiO_2 suspension getting a volume ratio of about 3:1 between CF and TiO_2 particles. Such suspension remained stable for about 1 h, whereupon a white sediment was observed. Anyway, each deposition was performed 1 min after ultrasonication.

PZTN powder with $\text{Pb}_{0.988}(\text{Zr}_{0.52}\text{Ti}_{0.48})_{0.976}\text{Nb}_{0.024}\text{O}_3$ nominal composition was synthesized by the mixed oxides route at 850°C for 4 h [28] and then milled down to 0.6 μm average particle size and 3 m^2/g specific surface area. The powder was then dispersed in ethanol by ball-milling with zirconia spheres, adding the same amount of alkyl phosphate ester and polyvinyl butyral as for the TiO_2 suspension, getting a 11.3 wt% solid content. The PZTN suspension was ultrasonicated and the settled coarse particles were removed. After this treatment the suspension was homogeneous and stable.

1 Particle size distribution of CF, TiO₂, and PZTN suspensions was measured by Dynamic
2 Light Scattering (DLS) (Zetasizer ZSP, Malvern) after 20 min of ultrasonication to ensure a
3 good dispersion of the particles. The morphology of the powders obtained drying the
4 suspensions was observed by a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM)
5 (Sigma, Zeiss).
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10 2.2. *Electrophoretic deposition, drying and thermal treatments*

11 The bilayer CF/TiO₂-PZTN structure to be produced by EPD on silver-coated alumina
12 substrates is sketched in Fig.1.
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32 *Fig.1 – Layout of stacked bilayer CF/TiO₂-PZTN structure.*

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35 EPD trials were performed in plane-parallel cell geometry and cathodic modality, keeping
36 the electrodes 1 cm apart and applying constant DC potentials up to 50 V. A house-made
37 alumina substrate (5 mm x 10 mm x 1 mm) coated by screen printing with a silver ink
38 (Chimet - Thick Film Division) and fired at 750°C was used as working electrode, while a
39 stainless steel 20 cm² plate was chosen as secondary electrode. For each deposition the
40 electrodes were dipped in about 50 mL of suspension. The values of the deposition current
41 density during the EPD process were recorded as function of time [27].
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48 The production of the bilayer structures was performed in four steps: i) the CF/TiO₂
49 composite layer was deposited on the silver-coated alumina substrate from the suspension
50 previously prepared, by applying 50 V voltage between the electrodes for 97 s; ii) such a
51 layer was dried in hot air at 80°C for 24 h and fired at 500°C for 15 min; iii) PZTN layer was
52 deposited at 30 V applied voltage for 45 s on the thermally treated CF/TiO₂ layer; iv) the
53 as-deposited bilayer was dried for 15 min in an initially ethanol-rich atmosphere (obtained
54 by placing 5 mL of ethanol in a 500 mL chamber) in order to reduce the rate of
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1 evaporation. Slow air circulation was then maintained for 24 h. The stack (bilayer on silver-
2 coated alumina substrate) was subsequently heat treated in a furnace at 800°C for 1 h in a
3 lead-saturated enclosure obtained by placing a zirconia cup upside down over the sample.
4 PZT pack was placed around the sample and on the rim of the cup to ensure lead
5 saturation during the sintering procedure. The temperature was increased at the rate of
6 100°C/h and decreased by natural cooling to ambient temperature.
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16 *Morphology and microstructure.* The structure of the consolidated layers was investigated
17 by SEM/EDS (Quanta, FEI) and XRD (Bragg-Brentano configuration, θ - θ) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$
18 radiation (D8 Advanced, Bruker). The SEM images were collected on top and fracture
19 cross section of CF/TiO₂ layer and on polished cross section of bilayer. The chemical
20 stability of CF, TiO₂ and PZTN after sintering was checked by EDS performed on a mirror-
21 polished cross section. XRD patterns were recorded in the range $15^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 80^\circ$, which
22 includes all the perovskite and spinel diffraction peaks. The scan speed and steps were
23 set at 2.4°/min and 0.02°, respectively. The mean crystallite size (D) of the sintered layers
24 was calculated by applying the Scherrer's formula, $D = k \lambda / (\beta \cos\theta)$, where k is the shape
25 factor, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the Full Width at Half Maximum, and θ is the Bragg
26 angle. The evaluations of β and θ were made considering the highest diffraction peak
27 between 20° and 40° - in order to avoid the peak asymmetry which could compromise the
28 profile analysis - with background-subtracted and Lorentzian correction of 0.037° on β due
29 the instrumental peak broadening. The shape factor (k) and the X-ray wavelength (λ) were
30 fixed at 0.9 and 0.154178 nm, respectively.
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44 The weight percentage of anatase and rutile was calculated by the Spurr and Meyer's
45 equation [29] using the integrated diffraction peak intensities of the strongest peaks of
46 anatase and rutile.
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51 *Electrical properties.* In order to pole and measure the dielectric, piezoelectric, and
52 ferroelectric properties of the sintered structures, silver paste was screen printed on the
53 top surface of the bilayer and then fired at 750°C for 15 min. The dielectric constant and
54 dielectric losses were measured as function of frequency in the 100 Hz - 1 MHz range at
55 room temperature using an impedance analyzer (HP 4194A, Hewlett-Packard).
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1 P(E). Hysteresis loops have been recorded applying sinusoidal voltage cycles of 60 V/cm
2 amplitude at the frequency of 1 Hz using a modified Sawyer-Tower circuit.

3 Poling was performed in silicone oil bath under a DC field of 3 kV/mm for 30 min, at 120°C.
4 After 24 h from the end of the poling process the sample's piezoelectric activity was
5 observed by detecting resonance and antiresonance peaks by impedance spectroscopy
6 measurements using an impedance analyzer (HP 4192A, Hewlett Packard). The
7 piezoelectricity was also investigated by applying a sinusoidally varying mechanical load
8 0.25 N amplitude at 110 Hz by using a d_{33} -meter (S 5865, Sinocera). The bottom electrode
9 was electrically connected to the bottom anvil of the d_{33} meter, and the upper anvil was put
10 in contact with the top electrode.
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20 **3. Results and Discussions**

21 *3.1. Particle size and morphology*

22 SEM images of CF and TiO₂ powders (Figs.2a and 2b) well agree with the particle size
23 declared by the suppliers (10 nm and 21 nm, respectively) and show quite narrow
24 distributions. Electron micrographs of PZTN particles (Fig.2c) suggest a particle size
25 distribution ranging between 30 and 300 nm. DLS measurements of the particle size
26 distribution in the CF, TiO₂ and PZTN suspensions to be used in the EPD process got
27 mean sizes (Z-average) about 20, 200, 1000 nm, respectively (Fig.3). The higher mean
28 values of particle size by DLS for TiO₂ and PZTN with respect to that determined from
29 SEM images (Figs.2a and 2b) is likely due to agglomeration phenomena occurring in the
30 concentrated suspensions prepared starting from the nanopowders and because DLS
31 gives a measurement of the diameter of the agglomerates rather than of the primary
32 particles as SEM does.
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Fig.2 – SEM images of CF (a), TiO_2 (b), and PZTN (c) powders.

Fig.3 – Cumulative particle size from DLS of CF (a), TiO₂ (b), and PZTN (c) powders.

3.2. Electrophoretic depositions and heat treatments

The deposition voltage-time curves for the CF/TiO₂ and PZTN suspensions are shown in Fig.4. They can broadly be considered as potentiostatic curves as the initial voltage peak is less than 5% of the set voltage. The CF/TiO₂ current density curve (J) does not have a strictly monotonic trend. In the early stage of deposition there is a quick decrease of the current density which might be due to the initial formation of a resistive ceramic deposit. The steady-state current density is reached at about 1 mA/cm². The applied voltage must be kept constant for at least 70-100 s to get a stucked CF/TiO₂ layer, otherwise film coagulation does not occur, even if mass transport is observed [26].

On the other hand, the PZTN current density curve has a more typical trend, customarily observed under constant voltage deposition conditions. In fact, as shown in Fig.4, the current density steadily decreases vs. time, which is likely due to the increasing electric resistance of the growing deposit during the whole EPD process [30]. The higher initial current density and slope of the PZTN curve with respect to the one of CF/TiO₂ indicate higher EPD efficiency and higher deposition rate from PZTN suspension.

This is mainly due to the higher particles concentration in PZTN suspension (11.3 wt% vs. 0.4 wt%). Moreover, during EPD the solid load of CF and TiO₂ in suspension reduces of about four times with respect to the reduction of PZTN concentration (2% vs. 0.6%). The lower concentration of CF/TiO₂ suspension and its higher percentage reduction prevail on the effect of the higher deposition voltage and time applied. Both depositions took place at the working electrode (cathode); no deposit was observed on the secondary electrode (anode).

Fig.4 – Deposition voltage (V) and current density (J) vs. time during EPD from CF/TiO₂ and PZTN suspensions.

3.3. Morphologic characterization of the bilayer structure

As shown in Figs.5 and 6, after heating at 500°C for 15 min the CF/TiO₂ layer results homogeneously cracked with formation of “islands” (Fig.5) covered by silver, as better highlighted in Fig.6, making the layer conductive. Even if CF and TiO₂ are dielectric phases the thickness of the CF/TiO₂ layer is quite thin. Moreover, the presence of diffused silver and cracks helps the deposition of PZTN as they further reduce the screening of the conductive substrate [31].

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During sintering the CF/TiO₂ layer possibly acts as a buffer, reducing the thermal expansion coefficients mismatch between PZTN layer and silver electrode, preventing in this way the peeling of the PZTN layer.

Fig.5 – SEM images of the CF/TiO₂ top surface after firing at 500°C.

Fig.6 – SEM images of fracture cross-sections of the fired CF/TiO₂ layer on Ag-coated alumina (silver in light grey).

XRD analysis performed on the CF/TiO₂ layer after firing at 500°C shows that even though cracking occurs in the CF/TiO₂ layer, this thermal treatment does not cause CF and TiO₂ particles to react with the Ag matrix (Fig.7). In fact, in the XRD pattern, distinct peaks of TiO₂ and CF (PDF Nr. 03-0864) appear and no other peaks due to possible reactions between them are present. TiO₂ is present in the starting powder as anatase (PDF Nr. 21-1272) and rutile (PDF Nr. 21-1276). The high intensity of the Ag peaks confirm the presence of the silver also in the top layer, while the low intensity and large broadening of the CF peaks is due to the small size of crystallites, about 10 nm. Firing at 500°C causes the crystalline size of anatase and rutile to slightly increase from 24.5 nm to 27.3 nm and from 44.1 nm to 48.1 nm, respectively. The weight percentage of anatase passes from 85.5 wt% in the starting powder to 83.0 wt% after heat treatment at 500°C. Such percentages were calculated by the Spurr and Meyer's equation [29] using the strongest peaks of anatase (1 0 1) at 25.2° and rutile (1 1 0) at 27.4°. Changes of both crystallite

size and relative amounts determined as above - although have comparable magnitude with the error of the technique and can be affected from a number of factors [32] - are in agreement with the pre-sintering temperature (500°C) that is lower than the anatase-to-rutile full transformation temperatures, and also too low for significant chemical reactions between CF and TiO₂ to take place.

Fig.7 – XRD analysis performed on the CF/TiO₂ layer fired at 500°C (lower) and sintered PZTN (upper) layers.

SEM image obtained by back-scattered electrons from CF/TiO₂ layer (Fig.8) shows that the darker TiO₂ particles (theoretical density 4.250 g/cm³) are dispersed in the grey CF matrix (theoretical density 5.304 g/cm³) and that particulate white phase is silver diffused from the electrode (theoretical density 10.5 g/cm³). All the TiO₂ particles show the same grey shades indicating that anatase particles (theoretical density 3.893 g/cm³) were fully transformed into rutile. Pure anatase in bulk phase starts to transform irreversibly to rutile in air at about 600°C [33]. However, the anatase to rutile transformation is a metastable to stable transformation, there is no equilibrium temperature and it's not instantaneous (since the transformation is reconstructive, kinetic factors are to be considered). This means that even if the sintering temperature is 200°C higher than the theoretical transformation

1 temperature, the time spent at temperatures higher than 600°C may not be enough for the
2 full transformation to occur. From EDS-SEM analysis it is difficult to find clear evidence of
3 the presence of nanometric anatase particles, even when there are indications (like
4 homogeneous grey shades and grains morphology) that the transformation is nearly
5 complete. On the other hand, the anatase to rutile transformation can be described as a
6 coarsening mechanism, whereby rutile nuclei grow at the expenses of anatase particles.
7 This could be the reason why the observed TiO₂ particle size is in the micrometer range,
8 even more when one considers that during the EPD process aggregates are deposited,
9 rather than primary particles. Considering the whole stack, Fig.8 shows also clean
10 interfaces between the different layers, and also between the TiO₂ and CF particles, where
11 no interdiffusion zone was observed. From image analysis across the CF/TiO₂ layer,
12 thickness, relative density, and volume percentage of the deposited TiO₂ and CF were
13 calculated. Such a layer, although cracked and filled by silver and PZTN, has a constant
14 thickness of about 6.5 μm and relative density higher than 96%. Image analysis confirms
15 that the deposition rate of CF and TiO₂ nanoparticles is comparable. In fact the volume
16 percentages of deposited CF and TiO₂ were 71.9% and 28.1% respectively. These values
17 are very close to the volume percentage of CF and TiO₂ in the suspension which was
18 74.9% and 25.1%, respectively. The same characterization was performed on PZTN layer
19 which consists of pure perovskite phase (PDF Nr. 33-0784) as shown in Fig.7. PZTN layer
20 shows a constant thickness (about 75 μm) and a porosity gradient along the cross
21 direction. The porosity seems to increase from the bottom to the top of the layer. It is
22 possible that the porosity gradient is an artefact occurred during the polishing of the cross
23 section due to the low cohesion of the PZTN grains achieved at the rather low sintering
24 temperature of 800°C. Anyway, such a temperature allows good adhesion and compaction
25 of the sintered layers, and a better control of flatness and thickness uniformity, which is
26 hardly achievable with higher sintering temperatures [34].
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Fig.8 – SEM images of the polished cross-section of the sintered CF/TiO₂-PZTN bilayer deposited on the Ag-coated alumina substrate.

3.4. Electrical characterization of bilayer

The real part of the dielectric constant (ϵ') and the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) of the bilayer structure vs. frequency are shown in Fig.9. At the frequency of 10^5 Hz, ϵ' and $\tan \delta$ values are 100 and 0.050 respectively. There is a lack in literature regarding the dielectric properties of PZTN thick layers, but anyway, these values are similar to those obtained for PZTN thin layers prepared by the oxide precursor method [35]. A frequency dispersion effect can be observed at high frequencies (higher than 10^5 Hz) in Fig.9b, which is often reported in the literature as being of the Maxwell-Wagner type, probably related to interface effects between electrodes and layers and/or between layers. Higher losses at lower frequencies can be related to extrinsic conductivity.

Fig.9 – Real part of the dielectric constant (ϵ') and loss tangent ($\tan \delta$) for the bilayer CF/TiO₂-PZTN vs. frequency.

The ferroelectric properties of the bilayer were obtained from the macroscopic electric field dependence of the polarization ($P(E)$) hysteresis loops, shown in Fig.10. The polarization P exhibits a hysteresis loop that depends on the sweep direction of the electric field E , thus confirming the ferroelectric properties. The remnant polarization P_r and the coercive field E_c are 11 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and 25 V/cm, respectively. However E_c and P_r values obtained here may differ from the true values of the material, because the conductivity effect was not separated. The distortion observed in the range of 50-70 kV/cm is probably associated with conductivity effects caused by the presence of the CF magnetic phase. The interface between the electrode and the PZTN layer and the space charges (e.g., oxygen vacancies at the interfaces between electrodes and layers), may also affect the measured values of the ferroelectric parameters.

Fig.10 – 60 V amplitude $P(E)$ hysteresis loop at 1 Hz.

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The piezoelectric response of the poled PZTN layer in the bilayer structure was verified by means of resonance impedance analysis. Fig.11 shows resonance curves of the sample in the $|Z|$ -phase format. We present impedance-phase plots for the three different ranges of frequency, over which the three characteristic resonances were observed. Fig.11a and 11b show the resonance observed at frequencies lower than 10^5 Hz, likely related to length-extensional vibration modes, while Fig.11c shows a resonance peak observed in the MHz range, probably due to the presence of a thickness vibration mode.

We do not present here piezoelectric parameters values, as piezoelectric parameters are usually determined by piezoelectric resonance as functions of the characteristic frequencies extracted from the impedance spectrum of suitably shaped samples. This method can only be applied to the ceramic materials with a well-defined geometry and presenting small losses, as confirmed by the maximum value of the phase angle approaching 90° (lossless condition). In our case, using the resonance method to calculate the piezoelectric coefficients would introduce considerable errors. Therefore, the occurrence of anti-resonance (minimum impedance frequency) and resonance (maximum impedance frequency) peaks in the impedance spectrum at reasonable frequency values can only be used to confirm the presence of significant piezoelectric activity of the piezoelectric layer.

Fig.11 – Impedance module Z and impedance phase angle vs. frequency over three different frequency ranges, highlighting three characteristic resonances: (a) and (b) low-frequency resonances; (c) MHz range resonance.

In order to confirm the piezoelectric properties we also measured the d_{33} piezoelectric constant ($50 \cdot 10^{-12}$ C/N). It should be noted that such a value is only indicative of piezoelectric response as this method is not appropriate for layer characterization. Though a value of the d_{33} coefficient in the range of several tens of pC/N provides unequivocal evidence of useful piezoelectric activity, in the present case such a low value could be due to the clamping to the substrate that constrains the lateral expansion of PZTN layer [36, 37].

4. Conclusions

CF/TiO₂-PZTN ferroelectric bilayers were produced by EPD on Ag-coated alumina. The first co-deposition of CF and TiO₂ particles from ethanol-based suspension created a layer 6.5 μm thick with the same volume ratio of the solid content in the suspension. After heat

1 treatment at 500°C the deposited CF/TiO₂ layer was homogeneously cracked in “islands”
2 wetted by the silver diffused from the electrode. The subsequent EPD of PZTN showed a
3 typical deposition trend characterized by a current density steadily decrease and resulted
4 in a layer of about 75 μm thickness. No evidence of new phase formation among the
5 deposited CF, TiO₂, and PZTN phases during the heat treatments was observed. The
6 produced bilayers are reasonably well-structured and display unequivocal evidence
7 piezoelectric activity. Moreover, such bilayers show good repeatability and reliability giving
8 the concrete possibility to be exploited in the production of many electronic devices, once
9 the ME coupling between the magnetic and piezoelectric phases will be optimized. Further
10 investigations will be performed to gain a full understanding of the properties of the bilayer
11 and to optimize the deposition parameters in order to obtain saturated P(E) loops with high
12 polarization and high permittivity. More accurate methods will be devised to enable the
13 determination of the piezoelectric coefficients in near-lossless condition.
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25 **Acknowledgements**

26 Technical support from Dr. Mauro Mazzocchi (CNR-ISTEC), Dr. Silvia Romano
27 (CERTIMAC) and Mr. Claudio Capiani (CNR-ISTEC) is gratefully acknowledged.
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30 Financial support from the “Progetto Premiale - Tecnologie e Sistemi Innovativi per la
31 Fabbrica del Futuro e Made in Italy” project funded by MIUR (Italian Ministry of Education,
32 University and Research) is gratefully acknowledged.
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